

**FORMATION OF A DISTRIBUTED FIELD WIRELESS SENSOR
NETWORK FOR REMOTE SENSING OF THE EARTH ON THE
EXAMPLE OF THE MUYNAK REGION**

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Annotation: The article describes the methods of digital remote sensing systems for real-time data transmission in groundwater monitoring, wireless sensor networks within wireless networks for monitoring landfills, network design and network communication. In the project of monitoring networks based on remote sensing of the earth, it is recommended to accelerate the processes of wireless network installation, data exchange and application of groundwater monitoring software. The structure and characteristics of a network of distributed field wireless sensors for remote sensing of land within the framework of island monitoring of groundwater are presented.

Key words: wireless sensor network, remote sensing, monitoring, network property, information transfer.

The development of many different remote devices for monitoring groundwater based on remote sensing of the earth is one of the important stages of modern scientific research. The main advantage of modern Earth remote sensing systems is that the registered electromagnetic waves can be immediately converted into digital form. At the same time, computer image processing, restoration and archiving of captured images are convenient and of great importance.

To date, the use of aerial photography in monitoring groundwater in the coastal zone of the South Island is of great importance. Digital remote sensing systems enable real-time data transmission, significantly improving data collection and efficiency. The installation of computer networks is of particular importance in monitoring groundwater. This helps to speed up the process of data exchange and the use of software tools along with a wireless network in groundwater monitoring.

Today, as industry experts know, most field-level transmitters are connected directly to controllers using analog cables. In data acquisition systems, sensors were individually connected, and analog multiplexing was expensive and was

only used when transmitting data over very long distances. Sometimes data collection systems even have problems connecting to the main system. Field operators used a laptop or other portable device to collect data, and then manually transmitted the data to the host system. Serial interfaces such as RS-232 or RS-485 were used to transmit this data. Higher-level controllers will be able to connect to the HMI system via the Modbus network. Enterprises can slowly implement stretched networks because they are non-deterministic, and when the network is heavily loaded, the delivery of some data packets can be significantly delayed.

Among wireless networks, wireless sensor networks are efficient and easy-to-use networks for monitoring polygons. It is important to design such networks and establish connections between the networks. Therefore, we design monitoring networks based on remote sensing of the earth as follows (Picture 1).

Picture 3. Structure of a network of distributed wireless field sensors for remote sensing of the Earth

The work is carried out on the proposal of a computerized groundwater monitoring system based on the information integration of groundwater modelling and decision-making processes. The information base of the computerized groundwater monitoring system is based on the use of continuous measurement of groundwater parameters (groundwater level, mineralization and temperature), which makes it possible to exclude the human factor from the human measurement process in order to prevent gross errors and impacts. .

This approach allows a network of wireless sensors to effectively solve the problem of data relevance by continuously measuring parameters in real time based on a network of sensors. It allows collecting data on the parameters of the aquifer and transmitting them to the computerized monitoring of groundwater.

Networks of wireless sensors are considered effective in creating a network monitoring system based on remote sensing of the earth. At the same time, wireless sensor networks are one of the promising areas for the development of modern telecommunication technologies; they have new functionality even when the cable infrastructure is replaced by radio broadcasting. The characteristics of wireless sensor networks are listed in the following order:

the ability to self-heal and self-organize;

- the ability to transmit information over long distances at low power of the transmitter (via a repeater);
- low cost of nodes and their small size;
- low power consumption and the ability to receive power from autonomous sources;
- Easy to install, no need to lay cables (thanks to fully wireless technology and battery power);
- The possibility of installing such networks without additional work on an existing and used facility;
- the ability to manage the WIRELESS SENSOR infrastructure using a tablet computer;

In the research work, the IEEE 802.15.4a standard offers a computerized groundwater monitoring and management system based on the integration of wireless sensor networks, which allows you to create a wireless data transmission channel with tens and hundreds of bandwidth. Operation of a computerized system for monitoring and monitoring the state of groundwater, data received from sensors of the wireless sensor network is transmitted via radio channels to the system server, which connects the stimulation software package running on the stimulator with a tablet computer.

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